

A whole genome atlas of 81 *Psilocybe* genomes as a resource for psilocybin production.

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Abstract

The *Psilocybe* genus is well known for the synthesis of valuable psychoactive compounds such as Psilocybin, Psilocin, Baeocystin and Aeruginascin. The ubiquity of Psilocybin synthesis in *Psilocybe* has been attributed to a horizontal gene transfer mechanism of a ~20Kb gene cassette. A recently published highly contiguous reference genome derived from long read single molecule sequencing has underscored interesting variation in this Psilocybin synthesis gene cassette. This reference genome has also enabled the shotgun sequencing of spores from many *Psilocybe* strains to better catalog the genomic diversity in the Psilocybin synthesis pathway. Here we present the de novo assembly of genomes of 81 *Psilocybe* genomes compared to the P.Envy reference genome. Surprisingly, the genomes of *Psilocybe galindoi*, *Psilocybe tampanensis* and *Psilocybe azurescens* lack sequence coverage over the previously described Psilocybin synthesis pathway but do demonstrate amino acid sequence homology to an alternative pathway and may illuminate previously proposed convergent evolution of Psilocybin synthesis.

Introduction

Psilocybin has recently been awarded breakthrough drug status by the FDA (Tullis 2021). Psilocybin has also been shown to be a safe alternative to traditional Selective Serotonin Reuptake Inhibitors (SSRIs) for the treatment of depression (Griffiths et al. 2016; Ross et al. 2016; Bogenschutz et al. 2018; Carhart-Harris et al. 2021; Davis et al. 2021). SSRI's have also been shown to be effective at reducing SARs-CoV-2 viral load (Schloer et al. 2020; Creeden et al. 2021; Dechaumes et al. 2021; Schloer et al. 2021; Zimniak et al. 2021). The mechanism of the viral interference is hypothesized to be related to the co-expression of ACE2 and Dopa Decarboxylase (DDC) which catalyzes the synthesis of serotonin (Attademo and Bernardini 2021). It is possible psilocybin's serotonin agonism will show promise in COViD treatment and prevention in the future, thus understanding the biological mechanism of synthesis is of increasing importance.

Two models have been proposed for psilocybin production in *Psilocybe*. Horizontal gene transfer has been thoroughly described by Reynolds *et al.* and Fricke *et al.*, while convergent evolution has been proposed by Awan *et al.* (Fricke et al. 2017; Awan 2018; Reynolds et al. 2018). Given the broad geographic distribution of psilocybe producing mushrooms and the history of human cultivation and selection for psilocybin producing strains, these models may not be mutually exclusive.

To address this question, we whole genome sequenced 81 *Psilocybe* spore samples to assess the sequence coverage over the previously well characterized *Psilocybe* synthesis cassette.

Results

In a whole genome sequencing survey of 81 *Psilocybe* genomes we noticed a lack of sequence coverage over the *Psilocybe* gene cluster described by Reynolds *et al.* for 5 of the 81 *Psilocybin* producing genomes (3 *Psilocybe tampanensis*, 1 *Psilocybe galindoi*, 1 *Psilocybe azurescens*). These genomes also exhibited genome-wide poor read mapping efficiency to the P.Envy reference genome with the exception of the mitochondria and ITS regions. These non-conical *psilocybe* synthesizing genomes share 99%, 100%, and 91% ITS sequence identity to a *Psilocybe tampanensis* sequence described by Rockefeller *et al.* (NCBI accession number: [MH220315.1](#)). The sequence from Rockefeller *et al.* was obtained in the wild and verified with photography of morphological features. The sequences described in this study were derived from spores that can be legally sold for taxonomy purposes but cannot be legally cultured to obtain morphological or chemical verification.

One other genus was labelled as *Panaeolus copelandia* but delivered two 100% identical ITS sequence to *Psilocybe cubensis* and *Aspergillus fumigatus*. This samples was omitted from further analysis. Sequencing and variant calling statistics are displayed in Figure 1 and Supplement Table 1.

Figure 1. (Left) Photographs of strains were obtained from the vendors public websites. (Middle Left). Sequence coverage of all contigs larger than 1Kb where coverage is on the Log Y axis and contigs sorted by length are on the X axis. (Middle Right) Assembly statistics from Quast 5.0. (Right Top) Number of Heterozygous and Homozygous SNPs detected with reads mapped to the P.Envy reference. (Right Bottom) Number of Reads for each run according to Samtools flagstat.

Colony Image	Assembly Coverage (Y) Large->Small Contigs (X)	Assembly Statistics (Quast 5.0)	SNPs vs HIFI P.envy Reference	homo %
Albino-Aplus-1-SW.fasta 	Assembly Albino_Aplus_1_SW # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 440 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 202 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 28,884,522 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 20,383,436 # contigs 2,756 Largest contig 288,367 Total length 39,899,494 GC (%) 46 N50 51,549	Albino-Aplus-1-SW-filtered.vcf.gz: 63,901 Hetero SNPs 303,723 Homo SNPs 355 Other SNPs	82.54%	
Albino-Aplus-1-PS.fasta 	Assembly Albino_Aplus_3_PS # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 395 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 200 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 28,898,128 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 21,902,895 # contigs 4,918 Largest contig 418,727 Total length 41,907,524 GC (%) 45.99 N50 53,469	Albino-Aplus-3-PS 108,232 Hetero SNPs 297,876 Homo SNPs 643 Other SNPs		
Bplus-1-redo-SW.fasta 	Assembly Bplus_1_redo_SW # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 425 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 208 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 29,576,179 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 21,778,514 # contigs 3,021 Largest contig 365,755 Total length 40,234,131 GC (%) 46 N50 55,195	Bplus-1-redo-SW-filtered.vcf.gz: 76,907 Hetero SNPs 307,249 Homo SNPs 460 Other SNPs	79.88%	
Bplus-2-redo-SW.fasta 	Assembly Bplus_2_redo_SW # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 402 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 212 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 30,095,279 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 23,254,442 # contigs 2,954 Largest contig 475,703 Total length 40,294,475 GC (%) 46 N50 64,581	Bplus-2-redo-SW-filtered.vcf.gz: 79,450 Hetero SNPs 311,282 Homo SNPs 473 Other SNPs	79.57%	
Bplus-3-redo-SW.fasta 	Assembly Statistics (Quast 5.0) Bplus_3_redo_SW # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 472 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 209 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 27,440,216 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 18,174,044 # contigs 3,305 Largest contig 304,795 Total length 40,252,110 GC (%) 46 N50 43,777	Bplus-3-redo-SW-filtered.vcf.gz: 78,314 Hetero SNPs 306,720 Homo SNPs 472 Other SNPs	79.56%	
Bplus-3-PS.fasta 	Assembly Bplus_3_PS # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 407 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 205 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 30,371,530 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 23,034,799 # contigs 6,793 Largest contig 475,703 Total length 42,910,400 GC (%) 46 N50 58,100	Bplus-3-PS 71,626 Hetero SNPs 328,799 Homo SNPs 513 Other SNPs	18%	
Burma-1-SW.fasta 	Assembly Burma_1_SW # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 424 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 206 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 29,825,594 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 21,860,498 # contigs 2,635 Largest contig 418,815 Total length 40,068,369 GC (%) 46 N50 60,029	Burma-1-SW-filtered.vcf.gz: 71,202 Hetero SNPs 307,914 Homo SNPs 423 Other SNPs	81%	
Chitwan-1-SW.fasta 	Assembly Chitwan_1_SW # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 376 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 148 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 23,349,709 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 15,430,988 # contigs 15,121 Largest contig 490,917 Total length 49,765,968 GC (%) 46 N50 20,914	Chitwan-1-SW 279,390 Hetero SNPs 320,623 Homo SNPs 2,216 Other SNPs	46%	

Colony Image	Assembly Coverage (Y) Large->Small Contigs (X)	Assembly Statistics (Quast 5.0)	SNPs vs HIFI P.envy Reference	homo %
ColombiaRust-1-SW.fasta 	Assembly ColombiaRust_1_SW # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 393 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 198 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 28,249,088 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 21,444,823 # contigs 3,424 Largest contig 640,766 Total length 40,812,283 GC (%) 46 NS0 55,984	ColombiaRust-1-SW-filtered.vcf.gz: 94,962 Hetero SNPs 320,910 Homo SNPs 711 Other SNPs	77%	
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference	
			Total Reads	20,503,304
			Mapped Reads	18,486,917
			Properly Paired	17,082,264
			Throughput (x150bp)	3,075,495,600
			Mapped Coverage	55.7
Ecuador-3-SW.fasta 	Assembly Ecuador_3_SW # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 416 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 209 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 29,655,078 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 22,233,921 # contigs 2,663 Largest contig 461,846 Total length 40,062,185 GC (%) 46 NS0 61,802	Ecuador-3-SW-filtered.vcf.gz: 75,572 Hetero SNPs 305,607 Homo SNPs 442 Other SNPs	80%	
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference	
			Total Reads	13,449,373
			Mapped Reads	12,293,602
			Properly Paired	11,827,624
			Throughput (x150bp)	2,017,405,950
			Mapped Coverage	38.6
GoldenTeacher-1-SW.fasta 	Assembly GoldenTeacher_1_SW # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 430 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 216 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 29,446,610 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 21,707,302 # contigs 2,829 Largest contig 419,991 Total length 40,096,272 GC (%) 46 NS0 54,698	GoldenTeacher-1-SW-filtered.vcf.gz: 81,236 Hetero SNPs 300,836 Homo SNPs 463 Other SNPs	79%	
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference	
			Total Reads	13,796,228
			Mapped Reads	12,600,180
			Properly Paired	11,382,064
			Throughput (x150bp)	2,069,434,200
			Mapped Coverage	37.1
GoldenTeacher-2-SW.fasta 	Assembly GoldenTeacher_2_SW # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 436 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 203 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 28,851,112 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 20,702,743 # contigs 2,872 Largest contig 388,781 Total length 40,015,197 GC (%) 46 NS0 52,001	GoldenTeacher-2-SW-filtered.vcf.gz: 74,465 Hetero SNPs 300,007 Homo SNPs 440 Other SNPs	80%	
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference	
			Total Reads	10,693,042
			Mapped Reads	9,668,091
			Properly Paired	9,181,532
			Throughput (x150bp)	1,603,956,300
			Mapped Coverage	29.9
GoldenTeacher-3-SW.fasta 	Assembly Statistics (Quast 5.0) GoldenTeacher_3_SW # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 406 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 207 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 29,861,146 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 22,744,406 # contigs 2,646 Largest contig 476,402 Total length 40,049,736 GC (%) 46 NS0 62,965	GoldenTeacher-3-SW-filtered.vcf.gz: 76,927.00 Hetero SNPs 305,227.00 Homo SNPs 463.00 Other SNPs	80%	
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference	
			Total Reads	15,563,000
			Mapped Reads	14,437,856
			Properly Paired	13,919,484
			Throughput (x150bp)	2,334,450,000
			Mapped Coverage	45.4
Huatla-2-redo-SW.fasta 	Assembly Huatla_2_redo_SW # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 412 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 205 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 28,949,662 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 21,468,140 # contigs 3,119 Largest contig 476,130 Total length 40,372,367 GC (%) 46 NS0 53,753	Huatla-2-redo-SW-filtered.vcf.gz: 78,658 Hetero SNPs 308,858 Homo SNPs 473 Other SNPs	80%	
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference	
			Total Reads	15,776,455
			Mapped Reads	14,316,074
			Properly Paired	12,348,270
			Throughput (x150bp)	2,366,468,250
			Mapped Coverage	40.3
Huatla-3-redo-SW.fasta 	Assembly Huatla_3_redo_SW # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 413 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 207 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 29,717,867 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 22,296,803 # contigs 3,567 Largest contig 365,511 Total length 40,739,035 GC (%) 46 NS0 60,365	Huatla-3-redo-SW-filtered.vcf.gz: 87,400 Hetero SNPs 318,428 Homo SNPs 576 Other SNPs	78%	
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference	
			Total Reads	37,123,705
			Mapped Reads	33,850,927
			Properly Paired	27,944,188
			Throughput (x150bp)	5,568,555,750
			Mapped Coverage	91.1
Huatla-3-PS.fasta 	Assembly Huatla_3_PS # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 414 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 209 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 30,168,678 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 22,825,751 # contigs 4,467 Largest contig 475,717 Total length 41,429,895 GC (%) 46 NS0 59,787	Huatla-3-PS 83,987 Hetero SNPs 314,602 Homo SNPs 536 Other SNPs	21% 79% 0%	
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference	
			Total Reads	61,449,088
			Mapped Reads	37,578,098
			Properly Paired	34,643,550
			Throughput (x150bp)	9,217,363,200
			Mapped Coverage	113.0

Colony Image	Assembly Coverage (Y) Large->Small Contigs (X)	Assembly Statistics (Quast 5.0)	SNPs vs HiFi P.envy Reference	homo %																																
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Maui-1-PS.fasta 	Assembly Maui_1_PS # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 414 # contigs (> 50000 bp) 205 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 29,452,034 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 22,002,607 # contigs 4,095 Largest contig 427,215 Total length 40,986,030 GC (%) 46 NS0 57,386	Maui-1-PS-filtered.vcf.gz: 80,550 Hetero SNPs 305,243 Homo SNPs 436 Other SNPs	79%	
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference Total Reads 17,965,377 Mapped Reads 15,758,926 Properly Paired 13,825,216 Throughput (x150bp) 2,694,806,550 Mapped Coverage 58.6	
Maui-2-PS.fasta 	Assembly Maui_2_PS # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 409 # contigs (> 50000 bp) 206 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 29,886,731 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 22,581,660 # contigs 6,625 Largest contig 419,705 Total length 45,574,135 GC (%) 45 NS0 48,868	Maui-2-PS-filtered.vcf.gz: 83,944 Hetero SNPs 310,689 Homo SNPs 509 Other SNPs	79%	
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference Total Reads 26,173,526 Mapped Reads 23,866,444 Properly Paired 19,625,166 Throughput (x150bp) 3,926,028,900 Mapped Coverage 64.0	
Maui-3-PS.fasta 	Assembly Maui_3_PS # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 436 # contigs (> 50000 bp) 207 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 28,956,206 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 20,760,963 # contigs 4,936 Largest contig 365,815 Total length 41,518,949 GC (%) 46 NS0 50,398	Maui-3-PS-filtered.vcf.gz: 86,311 Hetero SNPs 307,934 Homo SNPs 516 Other SNPs	78%	
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference Total Reads 23,974,761 Mapped Reads 21,580,667 Properly Paired 17,205,332 Throughput (x150bp) 3,596,214,150 Mapped Coverage 56.1	
Mazatepec-2-SW.fasta 	Assembly Mazatepec_sw_2 # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 392 # contigs (> 50000 bp) 174 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 25,717,867 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 18,040,409 # contigs 6,127 Largest contig 473,759 Total length 42,733,455 GC (%) 46 NS0 38,008	Mazatepec-sw-2 160,486 Hetero SNPs 266,548 Homo SNPs 827 Other SNPs	38%	
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference Total Reads 44,719,081 Mapped Reads 34,913,153 Properly Paired 26,598,220 Throughput (x150bp) 6,707,862,150 Mapped Coverage 86.7	
Penvy-Col4-PS.fasta 	Assembly Penvy_Col4_PS # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 456 # contigs (> 50000 bp) 118 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 19,584,623 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 7,943,088 # contigs 4,145 Largest contig 145,215 Total length 40,079,454 GC (%) 46 NS0 24,499	Penvy-Col4-PS-filtered.vcf.gz: 7,967 Hetero SNPs 120 Homo SNPs 1 Other SNPs	1%	
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference Total Reads 7,866,693 Mapped Reads 7,666,541 Properly Paired 7,491,900 Throughput (x150bp) 1,180,003,950 Mapped Coverage 24.4	
Penvy-Col5-PS.fasta 	Assembly Penvy_Col5_PS # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 473 # contigs (> 50000 bp) 175 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 25,200,410 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 14,698,824 # contigs 3,397 Largest contig 310,874 Total length 40,168,571 GC (%) 46 NS0 35,909	Penvy-Col5-PS-filtered.vcf.gz: 6,439 Hetero SNPs 108 Homo SNPs	2%	
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference Total Reads 8,355,714 Mapped Reads 7,997,413 Properly Paired 7,844,782 Throughput (x150bp) 1,253,357,100 Mapped Coverage 25.6	
Penvy-PS.fasta 	Assembly Penvy_PS # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 430 # contigs (> 50000 bp) 193 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 28,583,744 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 19,931,732 # contigs 2,903 Largest contig 432,304 Total length 40,326,453 GC (%) 46 NS0 48,911	Penvy-PS-filtered.vcf.gz: 5,204 Hetero SNPs 80 Homo SNPs	2%	
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference Total Reads 12,926,801 Mapped Reads 12,722,710 Properly Paired 12,430,620 Throughput (x150bp) 1,939,020,150 Mapped Coverage 42.2	
PES-Hawaiian-2-SW.fasta 	Assembly PES_2_SW # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 411 # contigs (> 50000 bp) 207 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 30,132,369 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 22,849,418 # contigs 39,619 Largest contig 525,905 Total length 96,653,390 GC (%) 46 NS0 5,833 Contaminated	NA		
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference Total Reads 76,252,588 Mapped Reads 41,861,666 Properly Paired 37,492,988 Throughput (x150bp) 11,437,888,200 Mapped Coverage 122.3	

Colony Image	Assembly Coverage (Y) Large->Small Contigs (X)	Assembly Statistics (Quast 5.0)	SNPs vs HiFi P.envy Reference	homo %
Pink-Buffalo-2-PS.fasta 	Assembly Pink_Buffalo_2_PS # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 418 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 206 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 29,423,534 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 22,024,000 # contigs 5,823 Largest contig 473,299 Total length 45,959,864 GC (%) 45 N50 46,916 Contaminated	SNPs vs HiFi P.envy Reference Pink-Buffalo-2-PS-filtered.vcf.gz: 80,659 Hetero SNPs 298,695 Homo SNPs 537 Other SNPs	79%	
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference Total Reads 23,463,617 Mapped Reads 20,874,201 Properly Paired 17,150,258 Throughput (x150bp) 3,519,542,550 Mapped Coverage 55.9	
Purple-Mystic-3-PS.fasta 	Assembly Purple_Mystic_3_PS # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 86 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 73 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 28,975,993 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 28,541,517 # contigs 1,967 Largest contig 1,793,965 Total length 31,203,043 GC (%) 48 N50 518,381 Contaminated	SNPs vs HiFi P.envy Reference NA Penicillium charlesii		
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference Total Reads 45,983,491 Mapped Reads 1,926,007 Properly Paired 1,758,992 Throughput (x150bp) 6,897,523,650 Mapped Coverage 5.7	
Samui-2-PS.fasta 	Assembly Samui_2_PS # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 379 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 187 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 26,141,217 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 19,544,790 # contigs 5,979 Largest contig 585,314 Total length 42,682,115 GC (%) 46 N50 41,638	SNPs vs HiFi P.envy Reference Samui-2-PS-filtered.vcf.gz: 183,630 Hetero SNPs 304,338 Homo SNPs 1,157 Other SNPs	62%	
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference Total Reads 20,867,283 Mapped Reads 18,094,375 Properly Paired 15,758,642 Throughput (x150bp) 3,130,092,450 Mapped Coverage 51.4	
Tampa-1-SW.fasta 	Assembly Tampa_1_SW # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 360 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 163 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 21,936,738 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 14,944,249 # contigs 8,126 Largest contig 380,796 Total length 45,421,653 GC (%) 47 N50 23,583	SNPs vs HiFi P.envy Reference Tampa-1-SW-filtered.vcf.gz: 12,535 Hetero SNPs 152,969 Homo SNPs 516 Other SNPs	92%	
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference Total Reads 23,619,770 Mapped Reads 2,659,886 Properly Paired 2,313,554 Throughput (x150bp) 3,542,965,500 Mapped Coverage 7.5	
Tampa-2-SW.fasta 	Assembly Tampa_2_SW # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 365 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 162 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 22,256,118 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 15,047,879 # contigs 8,096 Largest contig 366,246 Total length 45,514,260 GC (%) 47 N50 23,696	SNPs vs HiFi P.envy Reference Tampa-2-SW-filtered.vcf.gz: 13,341 Hetero SNPs 157,590 Homo SNPs 521 Other SNPs	92%	
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference Total Reads 24,119,178 Mapped Reads 2,757,448 Properly Paired 2,387,840 Throughput (x150bp) 3,617,876,700 Mapped Coverage 7.8	
Tampa-3-SW.fasta 	Assembly Tampa_3_SW # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 369 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 172 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 22,276,813 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 15,302,248 # contigs 7,974 Largest contig 365,796 Total length 45,100,156 GC (%) 47 N50 24,338	SNPs vs HiFi P.envy Reference Tampa-3-SW-filtered.vcf.gz: 10,491 Hetero SNPs 144,580 Homo SNPs 494 Other SNPs	93%	
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference Total Reads 20,113,293 Mapped Reads 2,060,006 Properly Paired 1,841,828 Throughput (x150bp) 3,016,993,950 Mapped Coverage 6.0	
Treasure-coast-1-PS.fasta 	Assembly Treasure_coast_1_PS # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 416 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 203 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 29,161,350 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 21,723,641 # contigs 6,763 Largest contig 691,902 Total length 43,128,291 GC (%) 45 N50 50,547	SNPs vs HiFi P.envy Reference Treasure-coast-1-PS-filtered.vcf.gz: 89,031 Hetero SNPs 315,992 Homo SNPs 573 Other SNPs	78%	
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference Total Reads 21,175,784 Mapped Reads 18,895,928 Properly Paired 16,019,266 Throughput (x150bp) 3,176,367,600 Mapped Coverage 52.2	
Treasure-coast-2-PS 	Assembly Treasure_coast_2_PS # contigs (>= 25000 bp) 407 # contigs (>= 50000 bp) 197 Total length (>= 25000 bp) 28,886,155 Total length (>= 50000 bp) 21,533,537 # contigs 4,502 Largest contig 681,105 Total length 41,282,649 GC (%) 46 N50 54,295	SNPs vs HiFi P.envy Reference Treasure-coast-2-PS-filtered.vcf.gz: 87,638 Hetero SNPs 320,016 Homo SNPs 624 Other SNPs	78%	
			Reads Mapped Back to P.envy reference Total Reads 22,500,883 Mapped Reads 20,707,883 Properly Paired 17,756,772 Throughput (x150bp) 3,375,132,450 Mapped Coverage 57.9	

Colony Image	Assembly Coverage (Y) Large->Small Contigs (X)	Assembly Statistics (Quast 5.0)	SNPs vs HiFi P.envy Reference	homo %																											
<p>Treasure-coast-3-PS.fasta</p>	<p>Assembly Treasure_coast_3_PS</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td># contigs (>= 25000 bp)</td><td>403</td></tr> <tr><td># contigs (>= 50000 bp)</td><td>187</td></tr> <tr><td>Total length (>= 25000 bp)</td><td>28,326,585</td></tr> <tr><td>Total length (>= 50000 bp)</td><td>20,685,425</td></tr> <tr><td># contigs</td><td>7,469</td></tr> <tr><td>Largest contig</td><td>705,512</td></tr> <tr><td>Total length</td><td>45,074,798</td></tr> <tr><td>GC (%)</td><td>45</td></tr> <tr><td>NS0</td><td>43,773</td></tr> </table>	# contigs (>= 25000 bp)	403	# contigs (>= 50000 bp)	187	Total length (>= 25000 bp)	28,326,585	Total length (>= 50000 bp)	20,685,425	# contigs	7,469	Largest contig	705,512	Total length	45,074,798	GC (%)	45	NS0	43,773	<p>Treasure-coast-3-PS-filtered.vcf.gz:</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>92,364</td><td>Hetero SNPs</td></tr> <tr><td>319,829</td><td>Homo SNPs</td></tr> <tr><td>630</td><td>Other SNPs</td></tr> </table>	92,364	Hetero SNPs	319,829	Homo SNPs	630	Other SNPs	77%				
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<p>Pailocybe azurescens-Hammond-OR-SW.fasta</p>	<p>Assembly OR_Coast_3_SW</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td># contigs (>= 25000 bp)</td><td>338</td></tr> <tr><td># contigs (>= 50000 bp)</td><td>146</td></tr> <tr><td>Total length (>= 25000 bp)</td><td>21,471,012</td></tr> <tr><td>Total length (>= 50000 bp)</td><td>14,812,928</td></tr> <tr><td># contigs</td><td>20,423</td></tr> <tr><td>Largest contig</td><td>452,736</td></tr> <tr><td>Total length</td><td>62,612,140</td></tr> <tr><td>GC (%)</td><td>46</td></tr> <tr><td>NS0</td><td>9,364</td></tr> </table>	# contigs (>= 25000 bp)	338	# contigs (>= 50000 bp)	146	Total length (>= 25000 bp)	21,471,012	Total length (>= 50000 bp)	14,812,928	# contigs	20,423	Largest contig	452,736	Total length	62,612,140	GC (%)	46	NS0	9,364	NA											
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<p>Georgia-2-SW-P.galindoi</p>	<p>Assembly Georgia_2_SW</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td># contigs (>= 25000 bp)</td><td>287</td></tr> <tr><td># contigs (>= 50000 bp)</td><td>109</td></tr> <tr><td>Total length (>= 25000 bp)</td><td>16,159,015</td></tr> <tr><td>Total length (>= 50000 bp)</td><td>9,991,753</td></tr> <tr><td># contigs</td><td>13,208</td></tr> <tr><td>Largest contig</td><td>380,798</td></tr> <tr><td>Total length</td><td>50,668,618</td></tr> <tr><td>GC (%)</td><td>47</td></tr> <tr><td>NS0</td><td>9,339</td></tr> </table>	# contigs (>= 25000 bp)	287	# contigs (>= 50000 bp)	109	Total length (>= 25000 bp)	16,159,015	Total length (>= 50000 bp)	9,991,753	# contigs	13,208	Largest contig	380,798	Total length	50,668,618	GC (%)	47	NS0	9,339	NA											
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<p>AA Plus Albino Cubensis Mush</p>	<p>Assembly AAplus_Mush_4</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td># contigs (>= 25000 bp)</td><td>467</td></tr> <tr><td># contigs (>= 50000 bp)</td><td>154</td></tr> <tr><td>Total length (>= 25000 bp)</td><td>23,195,783</td></tr> <tr><td>Total length (>= 50000 bp)</td><td>12,311,256</td></tr> <tr><td># contigs</td><td>4,970</td></tr> <tr><td>Largest contig</td><td>302,174</td></tr> <tr><td>Total length</td><td>41,345,670</td></tr> <tr><td>GC (%)</td><td>46</td></tr> <tr><td>NS0</td><td>29,208</td></tr> </table>	# contigs (>= 25000 bp)	467	# contigs (>= 50000 bp)	154	Total length (>= 25000 bp)	23,195,783	Total length (>= 50000 bp)	12,311,256	# contigs	4,970	Largest contig	302,174	Total length	41,345,670	GC (%)	46	NS0	29,208	<p>AAPlusPlus-ITW-filtered</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>185,470</td><td>Hetero (0/1) SNPs</td><td>57%</td></tr> <tr><td>250,854</td><td>Homo (1/1) SNPs</td><td>42%</td></tr> <tr><td>889</td><td>Other SNPs</td><td>0%</td></tr> </table>	185,470	Hetero (0/1) SNPs	57%	250,854	Homo (1/1) SNPs	42%	889	Other SNPs	0%		
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<p>A++ Leucistic Cubensis ITW</p>	<p>Assembly AAPlusPlus_ITW</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td># contigs (>= 25000 bp)</td><td>427</td></tr> <tr><td># contigs (>= 50000 bp)</td><td>190</td></tr> <tr><td>Total length (>= 25000 bp)</td><td>29,163,570</td></tr> <tr><td>Total length (>= 50000 bp)</td><td>20,995,341</td></tr> <tr><td># contigs</td><td>4,896</td></tr> <tr><td>Largest contig</td><td>522,421</td></tr> <tr><td>Total length</td><td>43,064,491</td></tr> <tr><td>GC (%)</td><td>46.06</td></tr> <tr><td>NS0</td><td>48,216</td></tr> </table>	# contigs (>= 25000 bp)	427	# contigs (>= 50000 bp)	190	Total length (>= 25000 bp)	29,163,570	Total length (>= 50000 bp)	20,995,341	# contigs	4,896	Largest contig	522,421	Total length	43,064,491	GC (%)	46.06	NS0	48,216	<p>SNPs vs HiFi P.envy Reference</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>122,411</td><td>Hetero (0/1) SNPs</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>288,488</td><td>Homo (1/1) SNPs</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>642</td><td>Other SNPs</td><td></td></tr> </table>	122,411	Hetero (0/1) SNPs		288,488	Homo (1/1) SNPs		642	Other SNPs			
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Throughput (x150bp)		4,469,469,300																													
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	Escondido-3-PS coverage Largest (left), Smallest (right)	Escondido_Mexico_Mush_1	Escondido_Mexico_Mush_1	Escondido-Mexico-Mush-1-filtered		
		# contigs (>= 25000 bp)	417	94,873	Hetero (0/1) SNPs	27%
		# contigs (>= 50000 bp)	197	257,007	Homo (1/1) SNPs	73%
		Total length (>= 25000 bp)	29,256,770	415	Other SNPs	0.10%
		Total length (>= 50000 bp)	21,531,350			
		# contigs	3,904			
		Largest contig	505,188			
		Total length	41,043,562			
		GC (%)	46			
		NS0	53,336			
				Reads	Mapped Back to	P.envy reference
				Total Reads		36,458,478
				Mapped Reads		30,396,009
				Properly Paired		24,116,478
				Throughput (x150bp)		5,468,771,700
				Mapped Coverage		78.6
	KOH-Samui-1-ITW coverage Largest (left), Smallest (right)	KOH_Samui_1_ITW	KOH_Samui_1_ITW	KOH-Samui-1-ITW-filtered		
		# contigs (>= 25000 bp)	399	124,119		72%
		# contigs (>= 50000 bp)	211	312,323		28%
		Total length (>= 25000 bp)	30,731,017	659		0%
		Total length (>= 50000 bp)	24,000,999			
		# contigs	3,739			
		Largest contig	688,740			
		Total length	40,883,548			
		GC (%)	46			
		NS0	66,025			
				Reads	Mapped Back to	P.envy reference
				Total Reads		27,224,662
				Mapped Reads		23,683,483
				Properly Paired		22,645,942
				Throughput (x150bp)		4,083,699,300
				Mapped Coverage		73.8
	KOH-Samui-2-ITW coverage Largest (left), Smallest (right)	KOH_Samui_2_ITW	KOH_Samui_2_ITW	KOH-Samui-2-ITW-filtered		
		# contigs (>= 25000 bp)	386	83,210	Hetero (0/1) SNPs	20%
		# contigs (>= 50000 bp)	207	341,168	Homo (1/1) SNPs	80%
		Total length (>= 25000 bp)	30,132,082	567	Other SNPs	0%
		Total length (>= 50000 bp)	23,771,428			
		# contigs	3,202			
		Largest contig	615,487			
		Total length	40,365,241			
		GC (%)	46			
		NS0	64,739			
				Reads	Mapped Back to	P.envy reference
				Total Reads		23,561,587
				Mapped Reads		20,322,490
				Properly Paired		19,457,514
				Throughput (x150bp)		3,534,238,050
				Mapped Coverage		63.4
	Leucistic-Ecuador-ITW coverage Largest (left), Smallest (right)	Leucistic_Ecuador_ITW	Leucistic_Ecuador_ITW	Leucistic-Ecuador-ITW-filtered		
		# contigs (>= 25000 bp)	427	89,225	Hetero (0/1) SNPs	23%
		# contigs (>= 50000 bp)	238	292,587	Homo (1/1) SNPs	77%
		Total length (>= 25000 bp)	35,753,987	515	Other SNPs	
		Total length (>= 50000 bp)	28,893,235			
		# contigs	5,639			
		Largest contig	564,890			
		Total length	48,644,135			
		GC (%)	50			
		NS0	73,098			
				Reads	Mapped Back to	P.envy reference
				Total Reads		40,096,169
				Mapped Reads		31,432,755
				Properly Paired		30,325,048
				Throughput (x150bp)		6,014,425,350
				Mapped Coverage		98.9
	LGT-1-ITW coverage Largest (left), Smallest (right)	LGT1_ITW	LGT1_ITW	LGT1-ITW-filtered		
		# contigs (>= 25000 bp)	415	82,290	Hetero (0/1) SNPs	22%
		# contigs (>= 50000 bp)	199	285,622	Homo (1/1) SNPs	78%
		Total length (>= 25000 bp)	29,715,858	487	Other SNPs	
		Total length (>= 50000 bp)	21,936,922			
		# contigs	2,790			
		Largest contig	457,023			
		Total length	40,058,931			
		GC (%)	46			
		NS0	59,842			
				Reads	Mapped Back to	P.envy reference
				Total Reads		24,161,169
				Mapped Reads		21,434,767
				Properly Paired		19,905,964
				Throughput (x150bp)		3,624,175,350
				Mapped Coverage		64.9
	LGT-2-ITW coverage Largest (left), Smallest (right)	LGT2_ITW	LGT2_ITW	LGT2-2-ITW-filtered		
		# contigs (>= 25000 bp)	413	73,884	Hetero (0/1) SNPs	
		# contigs (>= 50000 bp)	196	295,581	Homo (1/1) SNPs	
		Total length (>= 25000 bp)	29,906,883	506	Other SNPs	
		Total length (>= 50000 bp)	22,211,904			
		# contigs	5,277			
		Largest contig	656,212			
		Total length	42,006,142			
		GC (%)	47			
		NS0	54,365			
				Reads	Mapped Back to	P.envy reference
				Total Reads		34,689,256
				Mapped Reads		32,140,103
				Properly Paired		30,272,132
				Throughput (x150bp)		5,203,888,400
				Mapped Coverage		98.7
	Mazatapec-1-Mush Coverage Largest (left) Smallest (right)	Mazatapec_cube_Mush_1	Mazatapec_cube_Mush_1	Mazatapec-cube-Mush-1-filtered		
		# contigs (>= 25000 bp)	407	167,165	Hetero (0/1) SNPs	40%
		# contigs (>= 50000 bp)	152	248,597	Homo (1/1) SNPs	60%
		Total length (>= 25000 bp)	21,720,083	728	Other SNPs	
		Total length (>= 50000 bp)	12,686,167			
		# contigs	5,844			
		Largest contig	281,759			
		Total length	41,987,424			
		GC (%)	46			
		NS0	27,448			
				Reads	Mapped Back to	P.envy reference
				Total Reads		18,759,108
				Mapped Reads		14,711,081
				Properly Paired		12,420,122
				Throughput (x150bp)		2,813,866,200
				Mapped Coverage		40.5
	McKennail-PS-1 coverage Largest (left), Smallest (right)	McKennail_ps_1	McKennail_ps_1	McKennail-ps-1-filtered		
		# contigs (>= 25000 bp)	423	88,800	Hetero (0/1) SNPs	
		# contigs (>= 50000 bp)	219	306,796	Homo (1/1) SNPs	
		Total length (>= 25000 bp)	30,256,194	500	Other SNPs	
		Total length (>= 50000 bp)	22,888,055			
		# contigs	3,107			
		Largest contig	457,012			
		Total length	40,356,482			
		GC (%)	46			
		NS0	62,591			
				Reads	Mapped Back to	P.envy reference
				Total Reads		41,384,737
				Mapped Reads		34,022,584
				Properly Paired		27,287,044
				Throughput (x150bp)		6,207,710,550
				Mapped Coverage		89.0

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64 Assembly Coverage (Y) Large->Small Contigs (X)		Assembly Statistics (Quast 5.0)		SNPs vs HiFi P.envy Reference		homo %
	Assembly	Puerto_Rican_ITW	Puerto-Rican-ITW-filtered			
		# contigs (>= 25000 bp) # contigs (>= 50000 bp) Total length (>= 25000 bp) Total length (>= 50000 bp) # contigs Largest contig Total length GC (%) NS0	498 231 34,251,679 24,722,556 2,882 551,905 45,892,051 49 55,774	74,613 Hetero (0/1) SNPs 308,254 Homo (1/1) SNPs 430 Other SNPs		
				Reads Total Reads Mapped Reads Properly Paired Throughput (x150bp) Mapped Coverage	Mapped Back to Hetero (0/1) SNPs Homo (1/1) SNPs Other SNPs	P.envy reference 23,554,264 19,643,998 18,933,076 3,533,139,600 61.7
	Assembly	Roatan_Honduras_Mush_4	Roatan-Honduras-Mush-4-filtered			
		# contigs (>= 25000 bp) # contigs (>= 50000 bp) Total length (>= 25000 bp) Total length (>= 50000 bp) # contigs Largest contig Total length GC (%) NS0	399 179 25,827,341 18,018,963 7,637 554,928 47,427,061 47 30,655	169,104 Hetero (0/1) SNPs 261,261 Homo (1/1) SNPs 966 Other SNPs		
				Reads Total Reads Mapped Reads Properly Paired Throughput (x150bp) Mapped Coverage	Mapped Back to Hetero (0/1) SNPs Homo (1/1) SNPs Other SNPs	P.envy reference 30,863,295 25,631,741 19,471,640 4,629,494,250 63.5
	Assembly	Tosohatchee_print_ITW	Tosohatchee-print-ITW-filtered			
		# contigs (>= 25000 bp) # contigs (>= 50000 bp) Total length (>= 25000 bp) Total length (>= 50000 bp) # contigs Largest contig Total length GC (%) NS0	413 195 29,115,724 21,367,840 2,857 562,704 40,382,220 46 54,224	86,948 Hetero (0/1) SNPs 312,748 Homo (1/1) SNPs 549 Other SNPs		
				Reads Total Reads Mapped Reads Properly Paired Throughput (x150bp) Mapped Coverage	Mapped Back to Hetero (0/1) SNPs Homo (1/1) SNPs Other SNPs	P.envy reference 33,059,706 28,557,434 27,512,738 4,958,955,900 89.7
	Assembly	Treasure_Coast_Mush_2	Treasure-Coast-Mush-2-filtered			
		# contigs (>= 25000 bp) # contigs (>= 50000 bp) Total length (>= 25000 bp) Total length (>= 50000 bp) # contigs Largest contig Total length GC (%) NS0	406 198 29,076,168 21,719,924 3,718 858,451 40,787,192 46 56,861	101,847 Hetero (0/1) SNPs 317,701 Homo (1/1) SNPs 624 Other SNPs		
				Reads Total Reads Mapped Reads Properly Paired Throughput (x150bp) Mapped Coverage	Mapped Back to Hetero (0/1) SNPs Homo (1/1) SNPs Other SNPs	P.envy reference 36,946,681 31,278,159 25,471,922 5,542,002,150 83.1
	Assembly	Z_strain_3_PS	Z-strain-Mush-1-filtered			
		# contigs (>= 25000 bp) # contigs (>= 50000 bp) Total length (>= 25000 bp) Total length (>= 50000 bp) # contigs Largest contig Total length GC (%) NS0	418 214 30,075,292 22,718,875 3,199 419,245 40,448,407 46 60,688	263,386 Hetero (0/1) SNPs 248,041 Homo (1/1) SNPs 1,395 Other SNPs		
				Reads Total Reads Mapped Reads Properly Paired Throughput (x150bp) Mapped Coverage	Mapped Back to Hetero (0/1) SNPs Homo (1/1) SNPs Other SNPs	P.envy reference 25,240,783 21,707,698 19,529,440 3,786,117,450 63.7
	Assembly	Z_strain_3_PS	Z-strain-ps-3-filtered			
		# contigs (>= 25000 bp) # contigs (>= 50000 bp) Total length (>= 25000 bp) Total length (>= 50000 bp) # contigs Largest contig Total length GC (%) NS0	418 214 30,075,292 22,718,875 3,199 419,245 40,448,407 46 60,688	89,848 Hetero (0/1) SNPs 302,740 Homo (1/1) SNPs 477 Other SNPs		
				Reads Total Reads Mapped Reads Properly Paired Throughput (x150bp) Mapped Coverage	Mapped Back to Hetero (0/1) SNPs Homo (1/1) SNPs Other SNPs	P.envy reference 35,173,452 27,804,809 23,410,724 5,276,017,800 76.3
	Assembly	Thailand_Koh_Samui_Mush	Thailand-Koh-Samui-Mush-1-filtered			
		# contigs (>= 25000 bp) # contigs (>= 50000 bp) Total length (>= 25000 bp) Total length (>= 50000 bp) # contigs Largest contig Total length GC (%) NS0	389 126 20,892,367 11,874,858 10,693 414,879 46,572,765 46 20,342	372,431 Hetero (0/1) SNPs 187,310 Homo (1/1) SNPs 1,672 Other SNPs		
				Reads Total Reads Mapped Reads Properly Paired Throughput (x150bp) Mapped Coverage	Mapped Back to Hetero (0/1) SNPs Homo (1/1) SNPs Other SNPs	P.envy reference 23,763,422 19,149,594 15,333,410 3,564,513,300 50.0

Despite the low read mapping rates for *Psilocybe tampanensis*, *Psilocybe galindoi* and *Psilocybe azurescens*, the *de novo* assemblies of these genomes have high BUSCO completeness scores (93%) and matching ITS sequences suggesting they are indeed *Psilocybe* but differ enough at the species level to produce low cross species read mapping rates.

An alternative hypothesis is that these libraries are metagenomic or contaminated with non-*Psilocybe* fungi but still provide enough sequence coverage of the ITS region due to its high copy number. Contaminated libraries are usually detectable with bimodal sequencing coverage as its rare for the organisms to be equimolar. All 5 non-cubensis *Psilocybe* have very uniform sequence coverage across the contigs and high BUSCO completion scores with strong ITS sequence implying clean assemblies.

In combination, these data demonstrate close relatedness of *Psilocybe tampanensis* and *Psilocybe galindoi* but distant relatedness to the *Psilocybe cubensis* (P.Envy) reference genome. Given the known psilocybin production in these alternative *Psilocybe* species, these data also imply an alternative synthesis pathway must exist in these species as suggested by Awan *et al.*

Sequence Coverage Analysis

Uniform sequence coverage and high read mapping rates were observed over most of the of *Psilocybe* P.Envy genome for most of the strains (50 of the 81 are displayed in Figure 2 and Figure 3). A few notable higher coverage exceptions were the ITS region on Scaffold_9 and the mitochondrial genome represented by Scaffold_26. This is not a surprising result given the increased copy number of ITS and Mitochondrial sequences in fungal genomes.

A few smaller, repeat rich contigs (scaffolds 27-31) demonstrated more variable coverage across the *Psilocybe* genus. The ITS region on Scaffold_9 appears to be a tandem repeat which is collapsed in the reference sequence. Scaffolds 27, 28, 31, and 32 have telomeric ends and are small (171Kb, 117Kb, 69Kb, 33Kb). While these smaller contigs have variable coverage in *Psilocybe*, it is important to understand they represent less than 2% of the genome. Scaffolds 29 and 30 lack telomeric sequence and are 74Kb and 69Kb respectively. Three scaffolds have telomeric sequences on both ends. (Scaffold_2 = 4.3Mb, Scaffold_3 = 4.1Mb, Scaffold_9 = 2.3Mb) suggesting these are tip to tip chromosome assemblies.

The genomes most diverged from the P.Envy reference genome (*P. tampanensis*, *P. galindoi*, *P. azurescens*) exhibited very low read mapping rates. This is demonstrated by *P. azurescens* (OR-Coast) in Figure 3. This genome-wide low mapping rate was also observed in the *Psilocybin* production cassette on Scaffold_7 (Figure 4 and Figure 5).

Despite the low read mapping rates to P.Envy, *P. tampanensis* assembled into 23Kb N50 genome with a 93% BUSCO completeness score and a 99% identical match to Rockefeller *et al.* ITS sequence for *Psilocybe tampanensis*. These low mapping rates are reflective of a highly diverged species at the nucleotide level but to exhaust the exploration of psilocybin production, amino acid level homology was further explored.

Figure 2. Read mapping efficiency of species specific reads mapped to the P.Envy reference genome. Due to size limitations, only 50 genomes are presented. The remaining read mapping results can be seen in Supplement Table 1.

Figure 4. Integrated Genome Viewer (IGV) coverage plot over the Psilocybin synthesis pathway described by Reynolds *et al.* Strains *Huautla* and *Mazatepec* have complete sequence coverage while *P.azurescens* is lacking sequencing coverage over most of the genes.

Figure 5. Top-Heatmap of Illumina un-normalized raw sequence coverage of the Psilocybin synthesis pathway across 43 genomes. Low coverage genomes of the same strain (*Costa Rica* and *Samui*) were summed together. Bottom- IGV view of 3 strains with close homology to the reference genome.

Sequence coverage over Psilocybin synthesis cluster

To search for pathway redundancy, we utilized tBLASTn to identify alternative Psilocybin producing enzymes in the reference *P. Envy* genome. PsiK exists in the conical cluster on scaffold_7 but also has a close homolog on scaffold_1. The copy in the conical cluster on scaffold_7 has a unique SnpEFF high impact variant at p.Arg173Gly that only exists in *P. Envy* (Figure 6B). The copy on Scaffold_1 is missing the 5' Exon in *P. tampanensis*, *P. galindoi* and *P. azurensceus*, and is significantly diverged. The most closely related scaffold_7 PsiK amino acid sequences are seen in a multiple sequence alignment seen in Figure 6A. Further cloning and expression is required to confirm if this additional copy provides any pathway redundancy. Of interest, these alternative alignments are only partially clustered with PsiM and often PsiM is located in the middle of 80Kb contigs in the absence of other pathway related genes (Table1). This demonstrates a non-clustered Psilocybin synthesis pathway in the non-Psilocybe cubensis strains.

Figure 6A. Multiple sequence alignment using CLUSTALW of the most closely related PsiK genes in *P. tampanensis*, *P. galindoi* and *P. azurensceus*. The R173G mutation is also unique to *P. envy* when considering non-cubensis species.

Table 1. tBLASTn search of *P.tampanensis*, *P.galindoi* and *P.azurenscens* for PsiK, PsiH, PsiD and PsiM reveals a fragmented Psilocybin synthesis cluster with PsiM most often being on large but independent contigs disrupting the contiguity of the Psilocybin synthesis cluster.

	<i>P.azurenscens-OR-Coast</i>	<i>P.tampanensis_1</i>	<i>P.tampanensis_2</i>	<i>P.tampanensis_3</i>	<i>P.mexicana_Georgia</i>
PsiK_Contig	K141_2983	k141_15608	k141_5119	k141_12438	k141_3669
Contig Size	4,254	9,322	8,836	1,196	4,016
PsiH_Contig	K141_27478	k141_15608	k141_5119	k141_12438	k141_3669
Contig Size	40,681	9,322	8,836	1,196	4,016
PsiD_Contig	K141_27478	k141_11235	k141_11612	k141_12438	k141_17412
Contig Size	40,681	44,435	44,435	1,196	3528
PsiM_Contig	K141_27478	k141_1605	k141_16729	k141_1150	k141_18599
Contig Size	40,681	81,911	82,507	1105	880

Figure 6B. Variation map of PsiK, PsiD, PsiM, PsiH, PsiR -Scaffold_7. Grey is no alignment, Blue is reference allele, Aqua is low impact variant and Red represent High Impact SNPs as according to SNPeff.

JR316_008007-PSIK-scaffold_7

JR316_008011-PSID-scaffold_7

- AAPlicus.TTW
- AAplicus.Mush.4
- Arenal.Volcano.Mush.1
- Cambodian.ps.1
- Ecuador.3.P5
- Escondido.Mexico.Mush.1
- KOH.Samui.1.TTW
- KOH.Samui.2.TTW
- Leu.1.TTW
- LG72.2.TTW
- MDK.1.P5
- Mazataptec.cube.Mush.1
- McKennai.ps.1
- Orissa.India.TTW
- Orissa.India.Mush.1
- Orissa.India.Mush.4
- Orissa.India.ps.1.TTW
- P.Mexicana.Gallindoi.Mush.1
- Penvy.2.SW
- Panaeolus.Copelandia.Tropicallis.Mush.2
- Puerto.Rican.TTW
- Roatan.Honduras.Mush.4
- Thailand.Koh.Samui.Mush.1
- Treasure.coast.ps.1
- Treasure.coast.Mush.2
- Z.strain.Mush.1
- Z.strain.ps.3
- Albino.Aplus.3.P5
- Bplus.3.P5
- Chitwan.1.SW
- Costa.Rica.1.redo.SW
- Costa.Rica.2.redo.SW
- Huautla.3.P5
- Mazataptec.sw2
- OR.Coast.3.SW
- PE5.2.SW
- Purple.Mystic.3.P5
- B
- Golden.teacher
- Golden.teacher
- Golden.teacher
- Albino.Aplus.1.SW
- Bplus.1.redo.SW
- Bplus.2.redo.SW
- Bplus.3.redo.SW
- Brazil.corumbaa.1.P5
- Brazil.corumbaa.2.P5
- Brazil.corumbaa.3.P5
- Brazil.corumbaa.4.P5
- Columbar.Rust.1.SW
- X51.Costa.Rica.1.redo.SW
- X52.Costa.Rica.2.redo.SW
- Costa.Rica.3.redo.SW
- Ecuador.3.SW
- Georgia.2.SW
- Golden.teacher.1.SW
- Golden.teacher.2.SW
- Golden.teacher.3.SW
- Huautla.2.redo.SW
- Huautla.3.redo.SW
- Luminous.lucies.3.P5
- Luminous.lucies.P5
- Malabar.2.SW
- Malabar.3.SW
- Malabar.4.SW
- Malabar.P5.2
- Malabar.P5.3
- Mauli.1.P5
- Mauli.2.P5
- Mauli.3.P5
- Peny.C04.P5
- Peny.C05.P5
- Peny.C06.P5
- Pink.Buffalo.2.P5
- Samui.1.redo.P5
- Samui.2.P5
- Samui.2.redo.P5
- Tampa.1.SW
- Tampa.2.SW
- Tampa.SW
- Tampa.1.P5
- Treasure.coast.1.P5
- Treasure.coast.2.P5
- Treasure.coast.3.P5

- p.Ter440Ter
- p.Pro424Pro
- p.Cys413Cys
- p.Gly396Gly
- p.Asp394Asp
- p.Asp393Asp
- p.Gly392Gly
- p.His388His
- p.Gln387Gln
- p.Ser385Ser
- p.Val383Val
- p.Ala381Ala
- p.Glu380Glu
- p.Cys379Cys
- p.Thr378Thr
- p.Glu375Glu
- p.Gly372Gly
- p.Val369Val
- p.Leu368Leu
- p.Leu365Leu
- p.Ile363Ile
- p.Glu362Asp
- p.Lys361Lys
- p.Asp355Asp
- p.Ile356Ile
- p.Phe355Phe
- p.Ile353Ile
- p.Pro336Leu
- p.Pro335Pro
- p.Tyr333Phe
- p.Asn331Asn
- p.Pro329Pro
- p.Pro327Pro
- p.Asp326Glu
- p.Gly325Asp
- p.Thr321Thr
- p.Pro321Pro
- p.Ala320Ala
- p.Ala318Ala
- p.Phe317Phe
- p.Gly314Gly
- p.Pro313Pro
- p.Ile310Val
- p.Val307Leu
- p.Ile306Ile
- p.Gly304Gly
- p.Val302Val
- p.Ala300Ala
- p.Ala300Ala
- p.His298His
- p.Leu290Leu
- p.Leu290Leu
- p.Leu286Leu
- p.Leu286Leu
- p.Ile285Ile
- p.Ser284Ser
- p.Glu281Glu
- p.Thr277Thr
- p.Phe276Phe
- p.Tyr246Tyr
- p.Ser245Ser
- p.Cys241Cys
- p.Ala240Ala
- p.Ser238Ser
- p.Thr235Thr
- p.Val227Val
- p.Asn208Asn
- p.Asn208Thr
- p.Gly206Asp
- p.Gly206Ser
- p.Asp147Asp
- p.Lys144Lys
- p.Phe133Phe
- p.Ile119Ile
- p.Tyr117Tyr
- p.Tyr117Tyr
- p.Pro115Pro
- p.Gly113Gly
- p.Asp113Asp
- p.Gly110Gly
- p.Tyr109Phe
- p.Pro107Pro
- p.Ala106Ala
- p.Ile102Ile
- p.Asn97Asn
- p.Cys96Cys
- p.Glu94Glu
- p.Gln93His
- p.Gln93His
- p.Pro89Pro
- scaffold_7@2936989:A/C
- p.Phe78Phe
- p.Ile68Ile
- p.Ile68Asn
- p.Glu63Asp
- p.Gln62Gln
- p.Gln59Gln
- p.Tyr51Tyr
- p.Asn24Asn
- p.Leu22Phe
- p.Glu20Glu
- p.Ile12Ile
- p.Ala11Ala
- p.GlnArg

JR316_008010-PSIM-scaffold_7

JR316_008008-PSIH-scaffold_7

AAPPlus.ITW
 Aplus.Mush.4
 Aplus.Mush.1
 Cambodian.PS.1
 Ecuador.3.PF5
 Escudido.Mexico.Mush.1
 KOH.Samui.1.ITW
 KOH.Samui.2.ITW
 LFT2.2.ITW
 Leucistic.Ecuador.ITW
 MDK.1.PF5
 Mazatapac.cube.Mush.1
 Mckennall.pS.1
 Mckennall.pS.2
 Orissa.India.Mush.1
 Orissa.India.Mush.4
 Orissa.India.print.ITW
 PMexicana.Galindoi.Mush.1
 Penvy.2.SW
 Penvy.3.SW
 Penvy.4.SW
 Penaeolus.Cogelandia.Thailand.pS.1
 Puerto.Rico.ITW
 Roatan.Honduras.Mush.4
 Thailand.Koh.Samui.Mush.1
 Tosohatchee.print.ITW
 Treasure.Coast.Mush.2
 Treasure.Coast.Mush.3
 Z.strains.PS.3
 Albino.Aplus.3.PF5
 Bplus.3.PF5
 Chitwan.1.SW
 Costa.Rica.1.redo.SW
 Costa.Rica.2.redo.SW
 Huailfa.3.PF5
 Mazatapac.SW.2
 OR.Coast.3.SW
 PES.2.SW
 Purple.Myztic.3.PF5
 Golden.teacher
 P.Cubensis
 Albino.Aplus.1.SW
 Bplus.1.redo.SW
 Bplus.2.redo.SW
 Bplus.3.redo.SW
 Brazil.columbia.1.PF5
 Brazil.columbia.2.PF5
 Brazil.columbia.3.PF5
 Burma.1.SW
 Columbiakest.1.SW
 Columbiakest.2.SW
 X31.Costa.Rica.1.redo.SW
 X32.Costa.Rica.2.redo.SW
 Costa.Rica.3.redo.SW
 Ecuador.3.SW
 Georgia.2.SW
 GoldenTeacher.1.SW
 GoldenTeacher.2.SW
 GoldenTeacher.3.SW
 GoldenTeacher.4.SW
 Huailfa.2.redo.SW
 Huailfa.3.redo.SW
 Luminous.lucies.3.PF5
 Luminous.lucies.PF5
 Malabar.3.SW
 Malabar.PF5.1
 Malabar.PF5.2
 Malabar.PF5.3
 Maui.1.PF5
 Maui.2.PF5
 Maui.3.PF5
 Penvy.C04.PF5
 Penvy.C05.PF5
 Penvy.PF5
 Pink.Buffalo.2.PF5
 Pink.Buffalo.PF5
 Samui.2.PF5
 Samui.PF5
 Tampa.1.SW
 Tampa.2.SW
 Tampa.3.SW
 Treasure.coast.1.PF5
 Treasure.coast.2.PF5
 Treasure.coast.3.PF5

p.Ser7Phe
 p.Ile17Val
 p.Val22Val
 p.Gly30Trp
 p.Gly30Gly
 p.Ile34Val
 p.Ile34Ile
 p.Ile36Ile
 p.Pro37Pro
 p.Asn41Asn
 p.Glu47
 p.Glu47Ala
 p.Glu48Glu
 p.Leu52Leu
 p.Thr53Thr
 p.Leu55Leu
 p.Leu55Leu
 p.Thr102Thr
 p.Val104Val
 p.Glu106Glu
 p.Leu107Leu
 p.Gly109Gly
 p.Phe112Phe
 p.Leu114Leu
 p.Gly115Gly
 p.Ile117Ile
 p.Thr118Thr
 p.Asp121Glu
 p.Asp121Glu
 p.Arg122Arg
 p.Arg124Arg
 p.Arg127Gly
 p.Arg127Arg
 p.Ser135Thr
 p.Ser135Ser
 p.Lys137Lys
 p.Gly138Ser
 p.Gly138Asp
 p.Gly138Gly
 p.Ile139Ile
 p.Lys140Arg
 p.Phe142Phe
 p.His144His
 p.Lys148Lys
 p.His151Asn
 p.Ala174Ala
 p.Ser176Ser
 p.Ile177Leu
 p.Ile183Ile
 p.Leu185Leu
 p.Asp214Asn
 p.Asp214Ala
 scaffold_7@2928116:AG
 p.Lys236Asn
 p.Arg254Ser
 scaffold_7@2928294:GT
 scaffold_7@2928473:TJA
 p.Met306Leu
 p.Ala308Val
 p.Ala312Ala
 p.Ile353Leu
 p.Lys354Lys
 p.Glu355Glu
 p.Leu356Val
 p.Arg358Arg
 p.Arg358Arg
 p.Asn360Asn
 p.Gln361Gln
 p.Thr392Thr
 p.Leu396Leu
 p.Leu396Leu
 p.Asn397Asn
 p.Pro399Pro
 p.Glu400Gln
 p.Val401Asp
 p.Val401Val
 p.Pro403Pro
 p.Asp404Asn
 p.Asp404Asp
 p.Pro405Pro
 p.Ser406Ser
 p.Val407Glu
 p.Glu411Glu
 p.Arg412Arg
 p.Arg412Arg
 p.Leu414Leu
 p.Asp417Asp
 p.Lys419Lys
 p.Ala454Ala
 p.Gly453Gly
 p.Ala454Ala
 p.Glu463Glu
 p.Lys471Met
 p.Ter486Tpexit*?

JR316_008003-PSIR-scaffold_7

We constructed a phylogenetic tree (Figure 7) of the various genomes. Many of the genomes share strain names but were acquired from different spore banks (PS vs SW vs ITW vs Mush). These phylogenetically cluster together as expected. Many samples were sequenced multiple times as biological replicas and are represented in the sample nomenclature as Name_replica_vendor.

Conclusions

These data support both Reynolds *et al.* and Awan *et al.* in that Psilocybin synthesis appears to have evolved both a conserved ~20Kb cassette seen in many *P.cubensis* fungi but also a less clustered pathway in regards to a non-contiguous PsiM gene that still needs further characterization and scrutiny. Alternative psilocybin production has also been suggested in the cicada infecting *Massospora* fungi (Boyce *et al.* 2019). Taken together, these data underscore the need for further exploration of psilocybin genomics for alternative or redundant synthesis pathways. Given the divergence of the other Psilocybin producing mushrooms, simply mapping reads from other Psilocybe species to the *P.Envy* reference genome can be misleading. Until more complete references exist for the *P.tampanensis*, *P.azurescens* and *P.galindoi*, searching for conserved amino acid sequences more tolerant to synonymous DNA mutations will be required. The genetic variation in the species is substantial and these genomes will help to further correlate genotype to chemotype associations for this nascent field.

Methods

DNA Isolation

Spores were obtained from 4 vendors (Sporeworks.com, Premiumspores.com, Mushroom.com and InoculateTheWorld.com). Spore preparations utilized a modified DNA isolation procedure described in McKernan *et al.* Briefly 1.4ml of spores were centrifuged, decanted and resuspended in 200ul of ddH₂O. 25 µl of a Thaumatin-like protein was added and incubated at 37°C (Medicinal Genomics part #420206) for 30 minutes. 12.5 µl of MGC lysis buffer was added and incubated at 65°C for 30 minutes with 9 steel beads. Vortexing was performed every 7 minutes. Lysed sample were micro-centrifuged and 200µl of supernatant was aspirated and added to 250µl of Medicinal Genomics (MGC) binding buffer (MGC part# 420001) for magnetic bead isolation. The samples were incubated with the MGC magnetic bead mixture for 10 minutes, magnetically separated and washed two times with 70% ethanol. The beads were dried at 37°C for 5 minutes to remove excess ethanol and eluted with 25µl of ddH₂O

Library construction for whole genome sequencing.

Fragmentation

Genomic DNA (gDNA) was quantified with a Qubit (Thermo Fisher Scientific) and normalized to reflect 4-8ng/µl in 13µl of TE buffer. Libraries were generated using enzymatic fragmentation with the NEB Ultra II kits (NEB part # E7103). Briefly, 3.5µl of 5X NEB fragmentation buffer and 1µl of Ultra II fragmentation enzyme mix are added to 13µl of DNA. This reaction was tip-mixed 10 times, vortexed, and quickly centrifuged. Fragmentation was performed in a BioRad CFX96 thermocycler at 3.5 minutes at 37°C, 30 minutes at 65°C. The reaction was kept on ice until ready for adaptor ligation.

Adaptor ligation

The master mix for ligation was prepared on ice using 0.75µl of Agilent SureSelect Adaptor Oligo Mix, 0.5µl of ddH₂O, 15µl of New England Biolabs (NEB) Ultra II Ligation Master Mix, 0.5µl of NEB Ligation enhancer for a total reaction volume of 16.75µl.

Ligation was performed by the addition of 16.75µl of ligation master mix to the 17.5µl Fragmentation/End Prep DNA reaction mixture, incubate for 15 minutes at 20°C. To purify excess adaptors and adaptor dimers, vortex at room temp AMPure XP beads (Beckman Coulter

#A63881) to resuspend and add 16µl (approximately 0.45X) of resuspended AMPure XP beads to the ligation reactions. Mix well by pipetting up and down at least 10 times. Incubate the mixture for 5 minutes at 25°C. Put the PCR plate on an appropriate magnetic stand (Medicinal Genomics #420202) to separate beads from supernatant. After the solution is clear (about 5 minutes), carefully remove and discard the supernatant. Be careful not to disturb the beads that contain DNA targets. Wash the magnetic beads by adding 200µl of 70% ethanol to the PCR plate while in the magnetic stand. Incubate at room temperature for 30 seconds, and then carefully remove and discard the supernatant. Repeat the ethanol wash once for a total of 2 washes. Remove trace amounts of ethanol from the beads. Air dry beads for ~ 7 minutes while the PCR plate is on the magnetic stand with the lid open. Remove PCR plate from magnet and elute DNA target from beads into 10µl of H₂O, transfer 9µl cleaned DNA to a fresh well.

PCR amplification

Add 12.5µl 2x NEBNext Q5 Hot Start Master Mix (New England Biolabs #M0492S) to 9µl ligated DNA, then add 3.5µl NEB 8bp index primer/universal primer. The reaction was run the cycling program using 98°C for 30 seconds as an initial denaturization step. 6 cycles of denaturization, annealing and extension were performed cycling between 98°C for 10 seconds and 65°C for 75 seconds. A final 65°C for 5 minutes was performed with a final 4°C forever step.

PCR reaction cleanup

Resuspend room temp AMPure XP beads with a brief vortex. Add 15µl of resuspended AMPure XP beads to the PCR reactions (~ 25µl). Mix well by pipetting up and down at least 10 times. Incubate mixture for 5 minutes at room temperature. Put the PCR plate on an appropriate magnetic stand to separate beads from supernatant. After the solution is clear (about 5 minutes), carefully remove and discard the supernatant. Be careful not to disturb the beads that contain DNA targets. Add 200µl of 70% ethanol to the PCR plate while in the magnetic stand. Incubate at room temperature for 30 seconds, and then carefully remove and discard the supernatant. Repeat the ethanol wash once. Air dry beads for 7 minutes while the PCR plate is on the magnetic stand with the lid open. Elute DNA target from beads into 15µl of nuclease free H₂O, transfer 15µl into a fresh well.

Sample quality control and sequencing

Libraries were evaluated on an Agilent Tape Station prior to pooling for Illumina sequencing. Sequencing was performed by GeneWiz, Cambridge MA. A total of 690 million paired reads (2 x 150bp) were generated, averaging over 12 million read pairs per sample and a total sequence of 207Gb.

DNA Assembly

Reads were assembled with MegaHit v.1.2.9

(<https://academic.oup.com/bioinformatics/article/31/10/1674/177884>) (Li *et al.* 2015; Li *et al.* 2016). The Nextflow mapping and assembly pipeline is published on [GitHub](#). Quast 5.0

(<http://quast.sourceforge.net>) was used to calculate the assembly quality statistics (Gurevich *et al.*

2013). Sequencing data is deposited in NCBI under Project ID PRJNA700437 and PRJNA687911.

Read Mapping parameters

Reads were mapped to the P.Envy reference and to their own assemblies to generate BAM files and coverage statistics using bwa-mem (version 0.7.17-r1188).

```
bwa mem -R "@RG\tID:${id_run}\tPU:${id_run}\tSM:${id_run}\tLB:${id_run}\tPL:illumina" \  
-t $cpu -M $fasta_ref ${fq[0]} ${fq[1]} | \  
samtools view -hu - \  
| sambamba sort --tmpdir=. /dev/stdin -o ${id_sample}.bam
```

A workflow for this is deposited in github. https://github.com/mclaugsf/mgc-public/blob/master/AOAC_TYM_ERV/bwa-pair.nf

Variant analysis

Illumina whole-genome shotgun data (McKernan et al. NCBI Project: PRJNA687911) was mapped to the *P. envy* HiFi reference assembly using bwa-mem (version 0.7.17-r1188), samtools (version 1.8), sorted with sambamba (version 0.6.7) and variants were identified using bcftools (v1.10.2) (Danecek et al. 2021).

```
bcftools mpileup -Ou -f $(Hashemi et al.) ${bam} | \  
bcftools call -m -Ov | \  
bgzip -c > ${sample}-gvcf.vcf.gz
```

The VCF files were merged using bcftools and left-aligned to split up multi-allelic entries

```
bcftools merge *gvcf.vcf.gz --output-type v > merged.gvcf.gz  
bcftools norm -f /NGS/genewiz-june1st-  
10spores/ref/fungus/Psilocybe_cubensis_Envy_scaffolds.fa -m-any merged-norm.vcf.gz
```

The annotation from the *funannotate* pipeline was converted from gff3 format into SnpEff (v4.3t. 2017-11-24) database as described here (https://pcingola.github.io/SnpEff/se_buildingdb/)

Phylogenetic analysis

Phylogenetic analysis utilized APE (v5.3.) and SNPRelate (v. 1.20.1)(Zheng et al. 2012; Paradis and Schliep 2019).

Coverage analysis

Coverage analysis was performed using BAM files mapped to the P.Envy genome reference using bwa-mem as described above (Li 2018). BAM files were analyzed using pileup.sh from the BBmap version 4/30/2020 (http://bib.irb.hr/datoteka/773708.Josip_Maric_diplomski.pdf). The Heatmap was generated using Heatmap.2 from the gplots version 3.1.1 in R Studio (<https://www.rdocumentation.org/packages/gplots/versions/3.1.1/topics/heatmap.2>).

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